

INTEGRATING LEAN-AGILE PRACTICES AND SOCIAL SUSTAINABILITY IN OFFSITE CONSTRUCTION: A REVIEW

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18050477>

Abstract

The traditional method of construction poses a challenge to the growing demand of building activities. The challenges include waste, delay, delivery, quality control, and safety risks. Offsite construction (OSC) provides a solution to their increasing demand in housing and infrastructural activities. This literature review explores the lean agile practices and social sustainability in offsite construction and their effect on creating a balanced value chain. The findings highlight the need for technological innovation, flexibility, and adaptability in efficiently managing construction projects, which drives sustainable housing. Construction companies can leverage this to gain a competitive advantage while ensuring the well-being of stakeholders.

Keywords: Lean agile practices, social sustainability, and offsite construction

1. INTRODUCTION

The growing demand for affordable and ecological housing presents a significant challenge for traditional construction. The industry, historically reliant on labor and resources, has been slow to adopt lean-agile practices, which focus on minimizing waste, adapting to challenges, and maximizing value. This approach aims to reduce costs by eliminating waste and generating economic benefits. An agile approach specifically prioritizes delivering necessary products to clients, contributing to social sustainability (Alavi and Aghakhani, 2021; Obeidat, Al Bakri, and Elbanna, 2018). While distinct, combining lean and agile methodologies offers a holistic approach to fostering business resilience. Many cities in Nigeria, face problems like slums, traffic, and environmental degradation, demanding innovative and efficient solutions. These approaches, initially developed for software and manufacturing, are increasingly used by innovative construction companies to boost flexibility, iteration, reduce waste, and improve efficiency (Dallasega, Rauch, and Linder, 2020).

The offsite construction (OSC) represents a potential solution to the housing crisis as it generates less waste than the traditional methods. OSC is a method of building elements within a regulated setup followed by building them on-site, which hastens the construction process but at a lower cost and time (Lim, Sawab, Wang, Fan, Mo, and Li, 2021). The advantages of OSC include shorter

building times, higher quality, and less waste. Effective project management can optimize resource utilization, improve team communication, and minimize delivery time. OSC can also boost labor productivity, product quality, save energy, and lower emissions, addressing resource and labor shortages. However, OSC faces challenges in technological integration, stakeholder participation, and dynamic uncertainty (Chen, Guo, and Xue, 2023; Zhao, Chen, and Xue, 2023).

Integrating Lean Agile methodology can accelerate project completion, increase stakeholder visibility, and build stronger customer relationships. This methodology allows teams to adapt easily to changes and unexpected circumstances. It uses inventory management to eliminate waste by precisely tracking stored resources, preventing excess materials and over-hiring. Social sustainability measures a company's positive and negative impacts on its workers and community, as well as the quality of its stakeholder relationships (Gusmao Brissi, Debs, and Elwakil 2021; Jaillon and Poon 2008). This paper will focus on exploring the association between lean agile and social sustainability in offsite construction projects. It fills the gap in research on the effects of social sustainability on lean agile practices. Although general lean agile practices are well-discussed, the impact of the social sustainability dimension on projects and stakeholders has been given less focus. This research will explore the impacts of lean agile practices on social sustainability within offsite construction project management, including adoption challenges. By investigating these dynamics, the study highlights how lean agile practices affects social sustainability while considering its impact in the industry's growth in Nigeria.

The question raised include:

RQ₁: What are the dominant lean agile methodologies in offsite construction literature?

RQ₂: How do the lean agile practices contribute to social sustainability outcomes(e.g., employee safety, retention and job satisfaction) in offsite construction?

RQ₃:What are the key barriers and enablers to integrating lean agile practices for enhancing social sustainability in offsite construction?

The study also addresses a significant knowledge and geographical gap focusing on integrating lean agile practices and social sustainability, considering the number of construction activities that goes on in Nigeria. Existing literature often discusses the economic and environmental sustainability of offsite construction in other countries, but this study provides insights specific to the Nigerian context. This research will offer nuanced insights into adopting lean agile practices, suggesting strategies to improve construction projects.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Lean Agile Practice

The lean agile practice is an organized but adaptable approach to product development. Agile focuses on speedy and continuous delivery using shorter cycles, feedback at an iterative pace, and proper communication within the team. Lean is also efficiency-oriented and helps to eradicate waste, decrease expenses, and manage the workflow as well. As a result of manufacturing, lean construction is aimed at the eradication of waste to minimize process cycles, enhance product quality, and enhance project efficiency. The lean construction waste involves material waste,

delays, over processing, excessive motion, labor, and inventory. In spite of numerous studies on lean and sustainable construction being carried out in the developed nations, not much research has been conducted on the advantages of lean practices (LPs) within the Nigerian construction sector. This paper discusses the environmental benefits of lean construction in Nigerian building sector based on the analysis of cost and time parameters. It gives important insights into the way lean construction can assist a sustainable built environment in a developing nation. The combination of lean construction and other methods, including building information modeling and prefabrication, is gradually acknowledged to contribute to their productivity and sustainability in construction projects (Tezel, Taggart, Koskela, Tzortzopoulos, Hanahoe & Kelly, 2020; Li, Wu, Zhou and Liu, 2019). Integration of Lean, Green, and Building Information Modeling practices has enhanced the synergies among the concepts resulting in complex and sustainable construction projects (Saieg, Sotelino, Nascimento & Caiado, 2018). The studies have also revealed beneficial impacts on energy use and the reduction of carbon emissions due to the combination of prefabrication and lean (Heravi, Rostami, and Kebria, 2020).

Just-In-Time Practice

In the current world where land, buildings, labor, and energy prices are high, and concepts such as Just-In-Time (JIT) are adopted, the definite objective of the corporation is to decrease stock and accelerate manufacturing procedures. A large number of corporations have progressed towards the production pace that is based on the demand of the consumers rather than the push standard. Internal inventory will be able to be reduced with the help of this paradigm. In previous times, market conditions were different, and both producers and merchants concentrated on sales maximization by having large stocks and capacities of warehouses (Richard, 2014; Hardi, Hidayat, Hendrarini, and Setyadi, 2025). JIT also tries to minimize manufacturing and response time of suppliers to final customers. It is an amalgamation of a mindset, an approach, and a control system to make the process of managing and reducing waste in manufacturing efficient. It enhances the management of materials (Bamana, Lehoux, and Cloutier, 2019; Ahmed, Hossain, and Haq, 2021).

Value Stream Mapping

VSM offers an open outlook of flow decision-making. VSM removes the need not to design a blueprint on lean implementation. It helps in the design of the most efficient operation of the door to door movement (Mofolasayo, 2023). The flow of information and material can be identified with the help of value stream mapping. The VSM is the basis of developing and implementing improvement programmes. The combination of lean concepts and OSC have greatly helped streamline its production processes thereby eliciting significant potentials in dealing with resource wastages and low quality products. A great number of researchers have combined lean principles with VSM in order to improve the productivity and efficiency of the OSC manufacturing process and other industries.

VSM has been used in premanufacturing, factory production and design-to-assembly in offsite construction in order to optimize flow and minimize waste. Literature reports included shorter lead times, increased throughput, less rework, and better understanding of the opportunities of digital interventions in premanufacturing and production (Chen et al,2023), mapping of volumetric/modular production shows bottlenecks and allows line balancing and adjustment of takt, improved throughput and utilization (Chavan et al., 2025; Lei et al., 20), integration of VSM and BIM and simulation helped to reduce premanufacturing time by quantifiable percentages in

experimental studies (Barkokebas et al., 2021). VSM identifies systemic causes of defects and rework in offsite components to facilitate yield improvements at the first pass, and reduce corrective costs (Chen et al,2023; Daniel et al., 2022). Transport, storage and on-site assembly Mapping out reduces waiting, duplication, inventory holding across the supply chain (Daniel et al., 2022; Lei et al., 20). The quantifiable results of case studies are the multi-percent time savings in premanufacturing and the explicit definition of priority areas of improvement in slab and volumetric production lines (Barkokebas et al., 2021; Chen et al,2023;Chavan et al., 2025). Chavan et al., (2025), identified the inefficiencies in the production process of an offsite construction factory and develop strategies to mitigate through the use of VSM.

Business Process Reengineering

Bain (2023) explains, business process reengineering is the process of redesigning business processes completely, in order to gain massive improvements in quality, productivity, cycle times, and customer and employee satisfaction. The businesses start by identifying what needs to be done in order to add value to the customers. Process discovery, monitoring and improvement can be supported using such methods as process mining which includes analysis of event logs with information systems. Then they decide whether work should be done or how it will be done. The other critical aspect of business process reengineering is to reconsider the role of outsourcing or third parties. To gain high productivity, quality and customer satisfaction levels; in essence, BPR will compel enterprises to re-examine and overhaul their existing internal processes altogether. The principles of BPR are based on the belief that most organizational processes have been slowed down due to inefficiencies, duplications, and outdated processes (Jewell, Jewell, and Kaufman, 2022) and they will also affect the construction industry. BPR initiatives are driven by the need to enhance operational efficiency through the streamlining of the processes, elimination of wastes and reduction of the cycle times. To achieve the maximum resource allocation and resource utilization, this often involves workflow reengineering, automation of repetitive processes and the use of technology. BPR focuses on growth of quality throughout the board along with efficiency. Process redesign can ensure that organizations achieve the overall quality of their products and services by minimizing errors, defects, and rework (Trojanowska, Husar, Hrehova, and Knapcikova, 2023 Farayola, Hassan, Adaramodu, Fakeyede, and Oladeinde, 2023). Also, BPR is highly committed to giving its customers the best value through aligning the procedures with their needs and preferences. This customer centric approach is understanding the needs of clients, estimating their needs ahead, and designing processes that bring about products and services that exceed their expectations (Sheth, Jain, and Ambika, 2023; Fakeyede, Okeleke, Adaramodu, Farayola, and Oladeinde, 2024).

2.2 Social Sustainability

With an increased acceptance of sustainability in organizations, the trend of inculcating social sustainability in all aspects of business activities is on the increase (Ajmal et al., 2018). This strategic focus is seen as creating a favorable change and developing a competitive edge (Lee et al., 2021), which eventually leads to a healthy organizational performance (Orlitzky et al., 2003). Social sustainability boosts the reputation of the organization and causes customers to make purchases, which is then converted into better performance of the organization (Awan et al., 2020; Taher and Jaaron, 2022). Performance in organizations is not limited to the single goal of making the enterprise profitable to investors but it involves a twofold responsibility to consider the

environmental sustainability as well as the health of employees (Bernal-Torres et al., 2023). It is based on such ethical aspects and common workplace principles (Goyal et al., 2023). Thus, the management of social sustainability practices and company performance have positive co-relation (Sroufe and Gopalakrishna-Remani, 2019). Social sustainability practices have a positive impact on organizational performance of businesses (Najjar et al., 2024; Torkayesh et al., 2022; Tran et al., 2023).

Sustainability in construction projects is ecologically friendly design, building, and functioning of infrastructure and structures. Some of these include the use of renewable and non-toxic material, better energy efficiency and minimized trash. The concept of social sustainability is to provide spaces, which can meet the needs of the community; in addition, occupational health and community disturbance can be addressed by (OSC) as an active means; this is a people-oriented strategy that benefits social sustainability (Ahn et al. 2020; Hyun et al. 2021; Kordi et al. 2021). Numerous studies have implied that worker safety risk is less intensified in offsite construction than the traditional method due to the considerably reduced number of work-at-height activities involved in offsite construction schemes and, consequently, less accident (Ahn et al. 2020). In this way, offsite construction can offer workers safer and cleaner work environment. The well-being of employees and their cooperative behaviour are important factors that affect social sustainability (Pradhan et al., 2020). These basic features of sustainability, which give more weight to long-term perspectives, underscore the importance of enhancement of employee future potential (Staniskiene and Stankeviciute, 2018). Long term supplier-customer relations and stakeholder decision making can increase involvement, motivation, and communication between stakeholders, making the working environment more socially sustainable (Martinez-Jurado and Moyano-Fuentes, 2014; Baliga et al., 2019).

Employee Training and Development

Every industry relies on its employees to succeed. So therefore, training and development of employees is important. According to Mel Kleiman (2000), employees are worthy of training programs which are built on orientation, management skills, and operational skills of employees. Training and development may be initiated of one employee or a group of employees basing on the necessity to enhance performance as seen in a performance appraisal; on a performance improvement effort benchmark; on a broader or overall professional development program; on a succession plan to qualify an employee to be offered some form of change in role in the organization; or on a pilot of an employee or a trainee on a specific topic or skill (McNamara, 2016). The other motivation required by the training and development plan is the loyalty of workers and their efforts to move up in their job and their willingness to take on more responsibility and to bring in more meaningful contributions to the company.

Armstrong and Taylor (2020) define employee development as the process of training a worker within an organization in accordance with the needs of the organisation and the results, skills and preferences of the workers. In offsite construction, where there is interest in the introduction of improved technology, training and development is not readily available to the employees, which makes them feel stagnant and out of touch with the current trends in the industry. Training and development is not easily provided to the employees in offsite construction where there is interest in introducing better technology to the same and hence they feel stagnant and disconnected with the prevailing trends in the industry. The offsite construction implies the use of several types of

construction equipment, which significantly promote the automation of the construction process (Li et al. 2020; MacAskill et al. 2021) and offer safer and healthier working conditions to the construction workers and increase construction worker skills and training needs (Kordi et al. 2021). Employee training and developing should be treated as a valuable tool by organizations to develop employee skills, improve productivity, acquire a competitive advantage, and sustainability in order to survive in the dynamic business environment today and competitive advantage (Mohammed, Danjuma & John, 2022).

Employee Satisfaction and Retention

Turnover can adversely affect the performance and the long term sustainability of a business. As studies indicate (Smith et al., 2017; Johnson and Thompson, 2018), high turnover rate is a waste of resources and increases the cost of recruiting and training new staff. Additionally, the endless flow of new employees can affect the ability of an organization to meet its sustainability goals and may also change the dynamics within a team and reduce productivity (Doe & Johnson, 2019). Brown and Jackson, 2016; Williams et al., 2018 argue that companies whose culture is positive that embrace the importance of inclusion, well-being, and meaningful work have high retention rates. By making employees feel important and belonging to the mission of the organization, they will be more inclined to remain engaged (Smith and Martinez, 2020). There is a myriad of factors that affect retention, although several studies have determined that job satisfaction has the highest effect on turnover intention (Yang, Ju and Lee, 2016; Salau, Worlu, Osibanjo, Oludayo and Falola, 2018).

Also, a long-term employment promotes creativity and flexibility culture (Garcia et al., 2021), which helps abide by the social and environmental issues that are going to be addressed by the sustainable business. One should believe in the importance of competitive pay and benefits packages (Davis and Lee, 2017), career growth and advancement (Brown and Wilson, 2018), and skills development (Brown and Wilson, 2018). As Doe and White (2023) explain, new technologies and trends are expected to affect the rate of employee retention in sustainable organizations. Employee retention with respect to the construction industry is simply the capability to maintain skilled workforce which is the core of a successful offsite construction company. Talent retention is a process that was interpreted by McDonnell and Wiblen (2020) as a systematic method to attract, retain, engage, and develop talented employees. In order to attract, recruit and retain the limited labor force, organizations must continuously appreciate their employees which may take different forms including training and development. Talent retention is also a significant agenda to organisations throughout the world. Retaining good and talented employees is a critical challenge to the operations of organisations in any industry in both the emerged and the emerging economies (Adeniji et al., 2019).

The offsite construction alters the patterns of demands, as the job requires higher skills such as factory management, engineering, fabrication, and administrative occupations, and fewer onsite occupations, leading to retention whereby there is jobs redesigned (Assad et al., 2021). According to industry reports and reviews, there have been vast changes in the use of labor in modular builds and recurrent labor shortages throughout the sector that contribute to increased retention rate (Bertran et al., 2024; Bahr et al., 2021). The offsite projects demand new technical and managerial skills in different workforce categories and enhances training as a priority in order to retain and deploy employees in new positions (Assad et al., 2021). Modular strategies transfer a large portion

of conventional scope off-site to factories, shifting career paths and career stability to large numbers of workers (Bertran et al., 2024). Retention at construction-wide level is exacerbated by shortages and demographic pressures across the board as companies over smaller number of skilled workers (Bahr et al., 2021). There are unusual turnover dynamics related to the living conditions and management of operations recorded in pilot applications of prefab accommodations (Wang et al., 2016). The key strategies mentioned in the literature includes training to bridge skills gaps and maintain employability (Assad et al., 2021), system-based scheduling and multiskilling to smooth staffing requirements (Nasirian, 2022), enhanced living/operational arrangements to curb nonjob turnover causes (Wang et al., 2016), analytic workforce-planning systems to predict and manage turnover (Han et al., 2024), and knowledge-management systems to guard against organizational capabilities being exited by staff (Smith, 2024). The interventions have a focus on various retention drivers (skill obsolescence, schedule variability, nonwork conditions, planning uncertainty, knowledge loss).

Employee Safety and Wellbeing

Bhandari et al. (2020) emphasize that employee safety is what spells the long-term success of the construction sector. Awolusi et al. (2020) note that properly functional wearable sensing devices providing monitoring capabilities to health and safety of construction workers will depend on testability, applicable characteristics, and skilled personnel. fard, et.al (2017) describe how the safety of Off-site construction facilities aims to either detect the hidden causes of the safety events, behaviors within off-site project contexts with good predictive values of the safety outcomes. Lean approach has recognized a proactive safety risk management in OSC. To enhance OSC performance, it expects to minimize construction wastes, such as accidents (Bajjou, Chafi, and En-Nadi, 2017). It has been indicated that the lean philosophy eliminates most of the causes of accidents in the construction industry (Bajjou, Chafi, En-Nadi, and Ghosh, 2014; Carvajal-Arango, Bahamon-Jaramillo, Aristizabal-Monsalve, Vasquez-Hernandez, and Botero, 2019; Kalyuni, and Wodajo, 2024). In an attempt to maximize workplace design, Li, Han, Gul, and Al-Hussein, (2019), approved the use of visualizing tools to design how the assets of the construction will be setup on the site. Motion-based apps were proposed as the tool that helps to identify risky human behavior proactively to prevent accidents (Li, et al., 2019). As a strategy of managing safety in construction process, communication and safety training is recommended (Franks, 2018).

Wang et al. (2017) presented a wireless and wearable electroencephalography (EEG) system to assess construction workers' attention levels through brain waves. The study found that EEG waves can predict the perceived risk level of construction workers. According to Guo et al. (2017), wearable device data can accurately assess the psychological status of construction workers. The study investigated the correlation between workers' physical and psychological health. The study used wearable sensors to collect physical data and a questionnaire survey to acquire psychological data. The study suggests that workers' psychological status can be measured using physical data. Therefore, dangerous behaviors can be identified and investigated. Ogundipe et al., (2018) determined that lack of knowledge on safety education has inhibited safety managers capacity to organize safety activities and establish management of building production safety policy processes.

Ethical Orientation

Construction project managers rely heavily on ethical frameworks to help them make morally and responsibly informed decisions. Ethical frameworks offer a methodical way to assess and resolve ethical issues, guaranteeing that all deeds are in line with the more general objectives of justice, integrity, and accountability, claim Lurie and Albinsson (2020). Principles from well-known ethical theories like utilitarianism, deontology, and virtue ethics are frequently incorporated into these frameworks. To make sure that the advantages for the community outweigh any possible drawbacks, utilitarianism, which promotes actions that maximize overall happiness and well-being, can be applied to construction projects (Lurie & Albinsson, 2020).

Sullivan (2007) defines ethical orientation as a preference for one of two perspectives: teleology or deontology. Differing ethical orientations can lead to conflicts on what constitutes ethical behavior, sensitive situations, and ethical judgments. According to Barnett, Bass, & Brown (1994) and Forsyth (2008), ethical orientation plays a significant role in explaining disparities in ethical judgment among individuals. According to Barnett et al. (1994), ethical orientation has a significant role in understanding individuals' ethical decision-making in unethical situations. Brady (1985, 1990) distinguishes between two styles of moral reasoning: formalism and utilitarianism. Kohlberg (1984) identifies formalism (associated with Kantian ethics) and utilitarianism (associated with Bentham and Mills) as the two primary ethical principles, paralleling ethical deontology and teleology. Brady and Wheeler (1996) argue that the dichotomy between formalism and utilitarianism is crucial in the history of ethical theory. According to Nozick (1981), substantive ethics can be categorized into two appealing forms.

2.3 Offsite Construction

Offsite construction entails large amounts of production of building component in a factory setting as a way of contributing to the value of an entire project. Some of the components included in this approach are prefabrication, manufacture, modularisation, standardisation, pre-assembly of components, and modules (Taylor, 2010). Offsite construction is considered to get an extra push by overall improvements in manufacturing. It has been found to be a viable way of solving speed expectations and quality problems the construction industry is experiencing across the world. The use of these approaches enhances general competitiveness by the contractor (Sutrisna et al., 2022). In the short term, OSC can become the most common method of construction (Ofori-kuragu et al., 2021). This method of construction may increase by 34% of construction activity up to 55% of total output and offsite construction sector is estimated to expand by up to 4.5 times over the coming 10 years (Assad et al., 2022).

The use of offsite construction in the house provision comes with some of the following benefits, the production of a higher quality of housing, the production is faster at a lower cost besides being able to control costs better. Also enhanced are efficiency, minimised waste, mitigating effects of inclement weather, reduced labour and material needs and the overall effects on the environment without creating much disturbance to the residents [1]. Another potential solution to the decarbonisation of carbon is offsite construction (OSC).emissions, that would assist in overcoming the problems of the Nigerian construction industry (Wusu et al. 2022). It is associated with several advantages including: decreasing the number of tradesmen on-site (Arashpour et al. 2016), and better efficiency in assembling high-quality building components within a factory (Rahimian et al.,2017a), shorter construction time, lowering construction cost (Razkenari et al. 2020), lowering construction waste and increasing the continuity of workflows (Wuni, Shen, 2020) all of which

may lead to net zero building (NZB). Arashpour et al. (2016) confirm that the construction of OSC is superior to the traditional one construction industry methods. It has been proven that traditional construction sites in On-site and raise demolition and material handling contributes to the generation of the largest amount of waste in Nigeria. Health and safety issues (Wuni and Shen 2020; Wusu et al. 2022), and it was proposed that OSC can tackle this issue (Kolo et al. 2020).

3. METHODOLOGY

The research on the incorporation of lean agile practices and social sustainability in offsite construction used the available literature to develop concepts, variables, and relationship among variables. The authors were secondary sources since they reviewed archival literature of previous studies i.e. journal and conferences proceedings, magazines, books, internet sources etc. The concepts related to the research topic were used to discuss it.

4. ANALYSIS

This paper aims at conducting a systematic review on the topic of study. To establish the role of social sustainability in lean agile practice in offsite construction companies in developing countries, extensive review of literature in this field was done. The initial step was to obtain a list of the most valid, up-to-date, and pertinent research articles published in the famous publications. Additionally, fundamental principles of Systematic Literature Review (SLR) offer sufficient transparency and reproducibility as a research methodology. Article retrieval and screening are the two major steps in the research article search process. These are stages that are discussed in detail below.

Article Retrieval Phase

The retrieval stage was about retrieving the relevant research studies by using authoritative sources. The step entailed identification of the latest publications that cover the combination of lean agile and social sustainability. To have a complete and exhaustive list of pertinent literature, we made use of reputable scholarly databases i.e.: Google Scholar, Scopus, web of science, IEEE Xplore and Science Direct. The search was limited to finding articles that are published in leading and peer reviewed journals in the fields of construction management, sustainability, social sustainability, innovation. The keywords and search terms were the following: lean construction, social sustainability, ethical orientation, VSM, business process reengineering, offsite construction and just in time practice. The criteria of the articles to be included in the study were: the articles must be available in the indexed database, the articles must be relevant to the field of study, the articles should be published in the last five years (2018-2025) to ensure that only the latest developments and inventions on this area are captured in the study. Articles that were available in English were only included.

Screening Phase

The next stage was to screen articles retrieved in a wide range after the retrieval stage to select the relevant and qualitative articles. The process of screening was split into two steps; an initial screening and a thorough screening.

Initial screening

The articles collected were filtered on the basis of the titles and abstracts to establish the articles that were relevant to the research topic. Articles were also incorporated when they specifically discussed the subject of inquiry which is the application, intergration of lean agile practices and social sustainability in offsite construction. Articles that were not directly related to the main themes of the subject matter were rejected. Moreover, replicated articles were eliminated at this point.

Detailed review

Those articles which survived the filtering phase were further examined in order to evaluate the quality and content of their work. The full texts were reviewed to examine their methodological rigour, relevance of their results and how much they responded to the aims of this study. Specific consideration was made to:

- The strategies of the studies (qualitative studies, quantitative studies, or mixed methods).
- Geographical and sectorial bias, is toward the research of the developing countries.
- The lean agile concepts were labelled as whilst social sustainability themes.
- The difficulties and constraints that the authors had to mention related to the topic of study integration.

In this stage, articles were sorted out systematically in terms of their input towards comprehending the way in which social sustainability and incorporation of lean agile practices can influence offsite construction works. The studies were categorised based on the emphasis that their authors had on various phenomena such as VSM, JIT, BPR, employee satisfaction and retention, employee training and development, employee safety and wellbeing, ethical orientation and how they applied them to offsite construction projects.

Data Extraction and Synthesis

The data extraction was aimed at finding important insights of:

- The particular lean agile practices and social sustainability.
- The relevance to OSC.
- Gaps, finding and implications of existing knowledge or practice.

The information obtained in the papers was combined in order to develop a coherent image of the topic. The process of synthesis enabled us to see the trends, gaps, and opportunities of the future research and practical applications in the field. Figure 1 presents the summary of SLR.

Figure 1. Author PRISMA flowchart.

5. DISCUSSION

Managers should view the lean agile technique as a human centered operating system. VSM allows frontline workers to map safety risks and process waste; priorities BPR changes that eliminate manual handling, rework and exposure and add automation afterward. JIT buffers and cross-train to avoid rush induced strain, and visual management boards monitors a balanced set of KPIs, near misses, training completions, skills matrices, satisfaction pulse scores, retention reviewed in daily/weekly stand ups. Inculcating ethical orientation in practices allows for open door issue logs, anonymous escalation and acknowledgement of ethical problem solving. Investment in modular training routes (induction, task certification, team lead coaching), and rewarding these based on safety and development, not only throughput. Adopt stages through pilots, measure ROI in incidents and turnover reduction and scale what works through internal communities of practice and supplier joint kaizen. Concisely, plan the production system and the people system to have the gains in flow inseparable to gains in safety, learning and retention.

Barriers and Enablers to Integrating Lean Agile Practices for Enhancing Social Sustainability In Offsite Construction

The application of lean agile practice to improve the social sustainability in offsite construction (OSC) has both great prospects and difficulties. Studies show that ignorance and low awareness of lean concepts among the stakeholders hinder adoption and implementation of lean techniques in projects (Moradi, et al., 2023). Employees can also take lean initiatives to mean loss of job security, especially when automation and standardisation is involved (Nahmens and Ikuma, 2012). Therefore, employees resist to changes, which as shown to decrease the adoption of new processes and collaborative practice (Moradi, et al., 2023). Besides the ingrained hierarchical systems frequently having a negative effect on the introduction of collaborative and iterative systems (Jorgensen and Emmitt, 2009); the industry is also experiencing severe skill shortages, due to the lack of training in lean agile practices, and in soft skills that would allow people to collaborate effectively (Ahn et al., 2016).

The adoption of lean agile practice proves a higher probability of producing a positive impact on employee well being and retention when workforce development is linked to career progression (AlNuaimi et al., 2020). Thereby, lack of top management backing and dedication limits resource allocation and strategic change (Moradi, et al., 2023; Bayhan, et al., 2019). A robust leadership determination to human centred results, participatory working environments motivates frontline employees and joint training programmes serve as enablers (Forbes & Ahmed, 2011). However, short term bias in cost prevents investment in long term social outcome that is less easily measurable than financial results (Manley and Chen, 2015). OSC have unstable supply chains and insufficient supplier partnerships to enable just in time and pull productions [8]. The performance indicators are usually not standardized to ensure that social sustainability aspects like the safety of workers, equity, and well-being are captured (Opoku and Ahmed, 2014). Agile workflows, which enhance cross-functional teamwork and constant improvement, are also enablers in this area (Panas and Pantouvakis, 2010). Retrospectives and feedback loops when applied further to incorporate social indicators can assist organisations to be proactive on the issues of employee welfare and inclusivity.

Implementing lean agile within the offsite construction provides quantifiable social impacts, enhanced safety and working conditions, and community and workforce sustainability. Several reviews and empirical studies relate lean, offsite approaches, with distinct enhancements of social values in case of being combined with managerial and digital enablers. On site hazards and accident exposure to workers in offsite fabrication and lean safety integration is less than in onsite methods of the past (Sarhan, et al., 2019; Aslam et al., 2021). Ergonomics are enhanced at the factory and physical strain is reduced, as well as turnover is reduced in comparison to ad hoc site labour (Sarhan, et al., 2019; Aslam et al., 2021). Training that is accompanied by lean agile adoption increases workforce potential and contributes to the value, stable jobs in the manufacturing context (Malla, et al., 2023; Salama, et al., 2023). Rapid, more dependable delivery as well as enhanced quality can lead to a reduction in the number of disruptions to communities and enhanced occupancy results of housing projects (Aslam et al., 2021; Daniel et al., 2024). A local supplier development and upskill may be supported by supplier partnerships and modular supply chains when procurement is designed to incorporate social purposes (Salama, et al., 2023; Daniel, et al., 2023). Lean tools are also able to resolve numerous sustainability issues as demonstrated by systematic mappings, and this suggests that social benefits can be attained in cases where lean practices are directed (Aslam et al., 2021).

6. CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

This research work has examined the importance of integrating lean agile practices and social sustainability in the offsite construction projects with the understandings that is gained from the construction sector. While there is extensive research on the status of lean agile practices and social sustainability in developed countries, this research seeks to bridge the gap and deepen the knowledge the practices of the topic of study can impact the construction sector in Nigeria with an emphasis on sustainable building practice.

The study proved that the lean agile practice contributes immensely to construction sector in terms of GDP accounting for 3.17% of GDP in 2024 (National Bureau of Statistics, 2024). The construction sector faces a number of issues that affect sustainability, including substandard projects, prohibitive costs, delayed production, production of waste, loss of biodiversity, and disputes over social issues. There are social matters that stem from stakeholder conflicts, a lack of awareness, and having a significant effect on local communities; there are also issues developed within the environment, which include impoverished resources, pollution, and global warming; and the fiscal issues, which include unstable economies, increased cost, low profitability, and little or no generating value.

The findings of the study point out to the fact that there is a really important need to come up with new and better strategies of improving how the construction industry carry out projects in Nigeria and by extension developing economies. The policy recommendations highlighted here provide a clear direction about how the rights of all stakeholders involved can be secured and how the available support can be better coordinated to increase intergration of these practices, ensure wellbeing of employees, satisfaction of clients and ensure value creation, as well as sustainable building practice to reduce unnecessary backlash from regulators. Most importantly, this study notes that lean agile practices and social sustainability variable are quite useful in the interaction with offsite construction projects. Considering the technological innovation of the lean agile practices which minimizes waste and maximize value.

In order for the construction industry to evolve and contribute more effectively to Nigeria's economic prosperity, targeted reforms and continued government support are essential. This includes addressing the existing challenges of taxation, business registration, and financial access while fostering an social sustainability metrics and lean practices that encourages innovation, reduced turnover rate, safety and skilled labour within the sector. Ultimately, this research underscores the need for a more inclusive approach to other metrics and geographic areas, one that recognizes how this practices can affects other states in Nigeria and in other to support growth through sustainable and practical policy interventions.

7. LIMITATIONS AND FURTHER STUDIES

Overall, the study provides a validation of many of the findings outlined in literature, and at the same time suggests the need for further research in new areas as this study was context specific to Nigeria where regulatory frameworks, infrastructural challenges, and labor market characteristics may not reflect other Nigerian states or international settings, thus limiting generalizability. The following areas should be subject to future study: Longitudinal or panel designs should be employed in future research to determine a time order, integrate surveys with objective measures

(e.g., lost time injury rates, audited training hours, turnover record), and have multi source responses by frontline operatives and supervisors to mitigate common method bias. Mixed-methods case studies and ethnographies may deconstruct the interaction between visual management, VSM, and BPR and ethical orientation to create trust, voice, and retention. It can be tested using multi-level or SEM/PLS SEM models (e.g., training is a mediator between lean practices and satisfaction) or moderation (e.g., ethical orientation reinforces the JIT wellbeing relationship) and investigate nonlinear or threshold effects of practice bundling. Comparative analysis at Nigerian regional and peer market scales can determine context contingency, whereas the infrastructural reliability can then be treated as a boundary condition to be addressed by spatial analysis. Implementation mechanisms and costs would be revealed by design science or field experiments piloting digital VSM, BIM-enabled visual management or JIT supplier compacts. Lastly, policy oriented work ought to examine how incentives, enforcement of safety regulations or ethics in procurement can enhance the social sustainability payoffs of lean agile adoption in offsite construction.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author acknowledges the support of the project supervisor, Dr. Augusta and Dr. Nsikan John for his endless support during the manuscript writing. The author also acknowledges Covenant University Centre for Research, Innovation, and Discovery (CUCRID), Ota, Nigeria, for their support during the writing of this manuscript.

AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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